

Sarvaprataviveka:

A Path to Enlightenment

Outline

- ▶ Definition
- ▶ Worldview
- ▶ Methods and Practices
- ▶ Non-outcome

Defintion

- ▶ *Sarva* means all
- ▶ *Prakata* means to appear
- ▶ *Viveka* is the application of intellect or discriminative faculty
- ▶ Thus, *sarvaprakata viveka* is the application of the intellect to discriminate the appearance and disappearance of all things and phenomena, internal or external
- ▶ In one phrase: all that is, has arisen and will disappear

Worldview

- ▶ The world is empty of substance
- ▶ Only if it is cognized does it exist
- ▶ This is so regardless of the state - waking, sleep or dreaming

Methods and Practices

- ▶ Repeat application of the formula *sarvaprakata*
- ▶ This involves repeated discrimination into phenomena, with beginnings and endings
- ▶ Seeing everything with this angle of vision
- ▶ Calm and meditative, breath-regulated mind is the foundation for application of the above steps
- ▶ Pranayama methods such as *anuloma-viloma* or *kriya* breathing are positive steps in attaining the basis of calmness
- ▶ Any practice such as that of ethics and morality which leads to calmness is a foundational practice

Non-outcome

- ▶ Protracted practise extending over several years yields a calm mind and sharp intellect
- ▶ With these in hand one's day -to - day existence is also smoothed
- ▶ Thus there is no aspect of life which is not blessed
- ▶ And ultimately life is seen for what it is in itself